
STABILISING SOCIO-POLITICAL INSTITUTION IN OHAFIA IGBO OF NIGERIA THROUGH AGE-GRADE INTERVENTION.

¹Mba, Ahamefula Uka, PhD

Hezekiah University Umudi, Nkwerre, Imo State, Nigeria
Department of History & International Studies.

Phone Number: +234-8037368441, E-Mail Address: lifternent@yahoo.com

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²Mba, Charity Ahamefula

Hugh Goldie Theological Institute, Arochukwu, Abia State, Nigeria.
Department of Religious and Cultural Studies.

Phone Number: +234-7037510875, ihechilurum85@gmail.com.

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³Johnson I. Anene, PhD.

Hezekiah University Umudi Nkwerre Imo State, Nigeria.
Department of Public Administration

Phone Number: +234-8033390253, E-Mail Address: j.i.anene@hezekiah.edu.ng

ABSTRACT.

The role of Age Grade institution in Ohafia Igbo of Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. Since the emergence of this institution, it has not only contributed massively in the provision of social amenities, but has continued to sustain the bond of unity among groups in particular and Ohafia at large. The Age Grade Institution has encouraged the spirit of self-help among Ohafia people. Often time, the Age Grade Institution is known to have been engaged for the security of the community, thereby contributing to the Promotion of Political stability. They have also been engaged to enforce community levies, as well as maintaining law and order. Since membership to Age Grade spreads across, from teen age, up to the advanced years of adulthood, the rules and regulations safeguarding its formation have promoted the bond of discipline as well. This paper attempts to analyze the Origin and the roles of the Age Grade Institution in Ohafia Igbo of Nigeria, their impacts toward sustaining Socio-Political stability and how such could be harnessed towards Promoting Political stability in Nigeria in general.

KEYWORDS: Social Amenities, Ndi-Ezie Ogo, Ezi, Collaboration, Levies and Age-Grade.

INTRODUCTION.

In Ohafia Igbo of Nigeria, Age Grade institution accords recognition to youths' assemblage, and that is why as young as the age of ten, the Children born within the age space of two years have started organizing age set. This culture is known to have created an opportunity for the inhabitant to cherish competition and success. Among the Ohafia people, age grade institution has become a driving force in the provision of social amenities and the security of the land. They have formed formidable partnership with the traditional leaders, a situation that have created peaceful disposition in and around the community. Age grade system has remarkably reduced attention from the government in area of the provision of social amenities in Ohafia land.

Gone are the days when social responsibilities assigned to the age grade by the traditional leadership was merely sweeping and weeding of the market square, routine patrol of the Village boarder land for security reason, rotatory farm work on the Ezie's farm, the provision of log bridges across the brooks that crisscross the community etc. Currently, the Age-grade are now assigned some capital projects like the construction Hospitals, provision of recreation centers, building of modern toilets, postal agencies, culverts, building of schools, provision electricity etc. Recent studies have shown the age grades to have embarked on the tarring of roads and other high capital-intensive projects.

Because the age grades have become instrument of social change in the community, the traditional leaders have found them worthy partners in progress. As a result, their activities have been reinforced with political assignments like 'Uke Akpan' (Government task force). Prominent members of the age grade have often been nominated and later elected into the Ezie ogo leadership council. Many more have been given chieftaincy title in recognition to their services to the Community. The collaborative relationship existing between the traditional political leaders and the age grade has created mutual understanding devoid of rancor. This attitude has been responsible for prolonged peaceful disposition existing in every community in Ohafia land.

THE OHAFIA INDEGENOUS POLITICAL STRUCTURE.

Ohafia Political structure is confined to layers of units, from the unit to a larger group. This arrangement is in similarity to another Igbo group the Unwana people presently domiciled in Ebonyi State. Unwana is one of the seven Igbo speaking States in Nigeria. Agha U. Agha commenting on political structure in Unwana Igbo listed the following in ascending order, thus:

- (1) Family Rule (Ikwu).
- (2) Umunna Council.
- (3) Compound Administration (Ezi).
- (4) The Village General Assembly.
- (5) General Assembly. ¹.

Relatedly, Onwuka Njoku listed the following Political structure as it relates with the Ohafia people in ascending order, thus:

- (1) Onu Ulue (Nuclear Family).
- (2) Utuga Ezi (Minimal Lineage).
- (3) Ezi (Compound).
- (4) Isi Ogo.
- (5) Mba (The Compound). ²

In Ohafia land the Age Grade system plays significant roles in the leadership across the levels, likewise wealth or status. From the above account, it is not difficult to observe or noticed that power flows from the family. At that level of authority Njoku opines, thus, ‘the family authority composed a man, his wife or wives and unmarried children. Included in the household could be other dependents such as domestic slaves, clientele, pawns and relatives of the husband or wives’³. The impact of Age in taking both political and judicial decisions is well noted at this level of leadership. It is also the responsibility of the older family members to help in the upbringing of their younger relatives as this is remarkably societal assigned responsibility. Chieka Ifemesia in his own observed, thus, ‘In the best part of Igboland, generally there also existed what might be called Village democracies. Each community consisted of autonomous units, ranging from families, minimal and minor patrilineages through major and maximal lineages to entire Villages and Village-Groups’⁴. Agha in Webster and Boaken, ‘strongly maintain that Igbo society was therefore intensely democracies with a vigour characteristic of competitive egalitarian society’⁵.

In Ohafia land after Onu Ulue the next is Utuga Ezi (minimal lineage). Among the Unwana people, it is referred to Umunna. At the level of the Onu Ulue, Age also plays significant role in the Political, judicial and social relations among members. The older members of Utuga Ezi are referred to as the Ndi-ichin Utuga. According to Njoku, ‘the council is usually headed by the oldest member of the unit. The house of the oldest member usually forms the meeting venue. At this stage the unit could handle judicial and legislative matters and often settle cases involving residents. The younger people in the Unit are usually entrusted the enforcement the decisions of Utuga leadership Council.

After the Utuga, is the Ezi (the Compound). The Compound is made up of Umudi (People from the same descendant). Agha describes Ezi as, ‘consist of number of economically independent households, each with a man or woman as the householder. It is within the compound (Ezi) that you the patrilineal kindred of Umudi’⁶.

In Political administration of Ezi, Njoku has this to say, thus, ‘the affairs of the compound are in care of the council of Elders Ndi-Ichin Ezi’⁷. This council is presided over by the head of the most senior Utuga or the oldest in the compound. The premium attached to the Age or seniority In Ohafia Political system has made the system to be referred to as Gerontology.

At the Isi Ogo level, elders from various Ezi (Compound) are nominated to represent their wards in the council of Ndi-Ichin Isi Ogo or Council of Isi Ogo. At this level, the head of the most senior of the compounds serve as the head of the council. ‘Again, as the case at the lower levels of the hierarchy, the council performs legislative and judicial functions’⁸.

The Village Council (Ama-Ali) is the highest Political Unit in Ohafia. Here are the Ezie-Ogo in Council. Council members included representatives from the Isi-Ogo. In that respect, Ezie-Ogo in Council represents the highest level of effective Political and Social administration. Whatever decision taken here was final. The representatives of Isi Ogo formed the Ezie Ogo in Council. The Ezie Ogo who is conferred the title of the traditional ruler. He usually appointed from the most senior compound in the Village. Ezie Ogo represents the custodian of the sacred symbols of the ancestors as well as the communal land. The council acts as supreme court in judicial matter and also wields considerable moral and political authority.

THE AGE GRADE SYSTEM IN OHAFIA AND THE CONCEPT OF PROJECT EXECUTION.

In Agha’s submission with regard to the origin of Age Grade Formation, he stated, thus, ‘

The origin of Age Group in Unwana was simple and dynamic. There were two friends who exchanged visit, assisted each other in farm work, house making, construction of houses, helped each other when there was need. These two friends had children whose age differences were almost the same became friends and formed their own friendship group, like those of their parents⁹.

In that regard, Age Grade emerged through socialization of people of the same age set. The same apply to Ohafia where the newly formed age set often addresses each other as 'Ndi wu Enyi' (People who are friends). In order to deepen the bond or the ideology of Age Grade, Parents often contributed by pointing out to their children their age mates in the Community. This singular act has continued to draw inspiration to the young people.

G.T. Basden equally noticed the manifestation of the processes involved in Age-Grade formation through 'otu' (Club). He aptly pointed this out when he stated thus, 'Boys associated freely with their elders, but for games they consort with their own company ('otu')¹⁰. The 'otu' in most Igbo community where the Age-Grade institution is practiced, has formed the catalyst in the formation of Age-Set. This is because in the course of playing, parities are drawn between older children. In order to sustain the development of Age-Grade system, 'friendship formed in boyhood's days continued throughout life'¹¹.

Chieka Ifemesia in his account about the Origin of Age-Grade, stated, thus, 'Age set and Age-Grade cut across lines of descent, moreover; and although we do not know much yet about their Origin and early history, they are undoubtedly very old institutions. Obviously, their early development must have been connected with the usual association of young males from childhood to boyhood, including the formation of groups or companies for moonlight plays and wrestling competitions'¹². Stressing further on how the execution of social projects by Age Grade originated in Igbo land, Chieka further hinted, 'there must also have been the necessity to organize groups to carry out such public duties as the cleaning of the sources of water-supply; the building and maintenance of roads and bridges, village squares, assembly houses and deity shrines...'¹³. From the foregone account, it is certain that the listed social responsibilities could have contributed in reinforcing the cultural tenets of social responsibility by the people of Ohafia. At the same time the idea of releasing social responsibility according to age could have been formed.

While younger age grades could be assigned to sweep and clean the market square, much older age grades could build and maintain roads and bridges. In that respect, social responsibility was sustained in the cultural norms of the people.

In Ohafia, Age-Grades are assigned to recover communal levy. They could also be called upon to offer security services in time of threats. It therefore follows, that in Ohafia, social responsibility was assigned to the age-grade based on Age and the ability to perform assigned task.

Like in other Igbo communities where Age Grade institution and the assignment of social responsibility is recognized, the involvement of Age Grade social assignment begin minimal project under the supervision of an adult. From the small market sweeping assignment to the execution of capital projects as obtains presently. As a voluntary organization, the task of Age Grade as it is now, has gone beyond sweeping of the market, weeding of the pathway, but to the building of Hospitals, Schools, Bridges, Provision of Electricity, coal tarring of roads, building of recreational facilities etc. Before now Age Grade was centered in the community where they exist, but now due to rural urban migration in search of greener

pasture, members of Age -grades now live in various urban areas. The implication this, is the establishment of Age- Grade branch offices. While Age Grades have become formidable in every aspect of communal life the competition that it elicits among them is very healthy for community development.

Nevertheless, since provisions have been to accommodate everybody from teenagerto adulthood, competitions are bound to emerge. In other words, when Chieka maintained that ‘Age Grade were primarily organized for administrative purposes and they followed a more or less pyramidal structure, with the base made up of the youngest and the apex of the oldest’¹⁴. He was not far from the truth on the structure of Age Grade system where ever it is practiced in Igbo land. But recent research has shown the in some communities in Igbo land where Age Grade system is observed their social assignments and project execution term to be very silent.

When society has developed social responsibility, and took cognizance on whose shoulder the social assignments should rest, it was aimed at resolving communal social cohesion in order to sustain harmonious development.

SOME KNOWN AGE GRADES IN AMANGWUOHAFIA.

S/N	RIGHT-HANDED AGE GRADE	YEARS OF BIRTH OF MEMBERS	LEFT-HANDED AGE GRADE	YEARS OF BIRTH OF MEMBERS
1	ADINTI	1913-1916	NCHINA	1916-1919
2	OBIMBA	1920-1923	ENYIMBA	1924-1927
3	AKAHUWA	1928-1931	ONYIWA	1932-1935
4	UGWUMBA	1936-1939	AKAJIAKU	1940-1943
5	IKEMBA	1944-1947	UGOMBA	1948-1951
6	EKWUEME	1952-1955	IFEMBA	1956-1959
7	UDOJIMBA	1960-1963	ANAGHAUKA	1964-1967
8	ISHIBUMBA	1968-1971	IBUZOMBA	1972-1975
9	OBIMBA	1976-1979	IBUZOMBA 2 ND	1980-1983
10	OBIMBA 2 ND	1984-1987	IBUZOMBA 3 RD	1988-1991
11	OBIMBA 3 RD	1992-1995	IBUZOMBA 4 TH	1996-1999
12	OBIMBA 4 TH	2000-2003	IBUZOMBA 5 TH	2004-2007

AGE GRADES IN POLITICS AND THE PROMOTION OF POLITICAL STABILITY IN OHAFIA.

Age Grade institution has become an integral part of sustaining Political stability not only in Ohafia but to Nigeria in general. The engagement of the age-grade has not only promoted peace but has restored security and sustained social development.

As a matter of fact, Age is counted very important asset in Political Administration in Ohafia land in particular and among the Igbo people in general. In Ohafia the Council of Elders often referred to as the ‘Nzuko Ndi-Ichin’ is an important power block at various levels of Political leadership among the people. Apart from being saddled with Political responsibilities, the council of Elders is known to have been involved in the performance of the judicial duties as well. In view of the above assertion, Age has always been considered as paramount to the election of every Political office. It is cultural with the people. In addition, the oldest family member could also be appointed to lead at any level of Political leadership in Ohafia.

In other words, in a situation where a young person is appointed to lead by virtue of having come from the oldest family, older members of such family could rally around to offer useful Political and Judicial advice. This is a clear demonstration of Age consideration in performing certain Political and Judicial functions in Ohafia. Agha rightly observed this when he stated, thus, ‘the oldest person is the head of each lineage and every case or matter that affect the family especially if the defaulters are from the same kindred is settled within by him’¹⁵. Council of Ndi-Ichin Ezi combines their political authority to resolve family matter. Apart from Political and Judicial matter, the council can impose sanction and then, mobilize the younger male from the family to enforce it.

Considering the levels of Political administration in Ohafia land, it is obvious to say that Political system in Ohafia is not only rigid but segmentary as well. It is closely knitted. Hardly would any matter escape without being properly attended to. Cases from this level can only be taken to the higher authority, ‘if the offenders are not of the same family but are from the same compound’¹⁶. Political structure at the family level is therefore made up of the oldest person in the lineage and every adult male born into such family. They usually meet at the Obi of the oldest member when there is need.

Utuga Ezi is the next Political Unit after the family in Ohafia Political structure. This is made up of a set of nuclear paternal households claiming descent from a common father. Politically, the head or leader is appointed from the family of the founder of the Utuga Ezi. His cabinet is formed from the heads of the component nuclear families. In the cabinet younger men of proven ability could be nominated to join the council of Ndi-Ichin Utuga Ezi.

Ndi-Ichin also deliberate on matters and adjudicate on cases that happened within Utuga Ezi. Cases or offences committed against the land are usually referred to the Ama Ala. Cases like theft, fighting and the use of abusive words against member of the Utuga Ezi are some of the issues handled by council of Ndi-Ichin. The council also enforces the directives from the Ama Ala (The Village). In effect, leadership assignment at this level involves judicial and legislative matters.

At the Ezi level, the political structure is more pronounced. The obu the symbol of Political authority is usually erected to serve various functions. At this level too, the compounds that constitute the Ezi usually send representatives to the council of Ezie-Ezi. The Ezi council could entertain appeal cases from the lower units, even as the obu which is permanent headquarters of the Ezi apart being used as the legislative and judicial house, could also serve as ‘Political, ritual and recreational functions’¹⁷. It is also at the Obu, that the ‘Ududu Umudi’(Memorial Ornament of the Patrilineal Ancestors) are kept.

Isi-Ogo is the next. It follows the same procedure of having representatives drawn from the Ezi to form the council of Ndi-Ichin Isi-Ogo. They hear appeal from the lower units, and could refer serious matter to the highest body the Ama Ala.

Mba (Village) is the highest Political Unit. The leader known as the Ezie-Ogo is appointed from the ruling family. They lead the community with the laid down procedures and handle matters referred to it from the lower units. Ezie-Ogo cabinet is made up of prominent people, who are culturally versed with the tradition of the people. They have the authority to inform the public on days of important events, and can take final decision referred to it. Certainly, judicial matters are reserved for the council of Ama Ala under the leadership of Ezie -Ogo. In Ohafia land, certain offences are better handled by the Ezie-Ogo-In-Council. Crimes like murder, incest, adultery, stealing of yam, desecration of the deity, poisoning, witchcraft and many more are some the offences reported directly to Ezie-Ogo in Council.

Great warriors and prominent farmers could be inducted into the council of Ezie Ogo the highest political body in Ohafia land. Warriors could advise Ezie Ogo in council on matters related to war. For such people age do not count much but contribution to the wellbeing of the community. In olden days great farmers were often inducted having acquired the revered 'Ogbuji title'.

AGE GRADE SYSTEM AS AN AGENT OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC STABILITY IN NIGERIA.

Before the advent of white men to Ohafia, Age Grade had been the back bone of Economic sustenance, then rural urban drift was very low. Majority of the people lived in the rural areas, with farming providing over 90% of employment. Cash was difficult to come by, but the Age-Grades were able to form cooperative society where members took turns to work for each other free of charge. This idea attracted more people to farm work, even as the farm output was able to sustain the rural dwellers all through the season.

In Ohafia land, through the intervention of the Age-Grade, people no longer depend on the government solely for the provision of social amenities. This is because, it is culturally, imbued on the people to live by self-reliance. The consequence of that is that people now compete through the age grades to provide such amenities with little or no attention to government intervention.

In effect, considering the fact that some of the projects are becoming capital intensive, age grades have resorted to collaboration with the government to execute them. This is a welcome development, as such partnership has boosted peace and sustained economic development. In the days of DFRRRI in Nigeria Age Grades have partnered with the government to construct feeder roads to farm land. Through such intervention, rural farmers were able not only to evacuate their farm produce but also make some cash.

Age Grade Partnership with the government could be traced beyond now. For instance, Okorie Uma, had stated, thus, 'when the present Nigerian Railway tracks were being constructed from Port Harcourt to Maiduguri our fathers worked on the construction...Ohafia communities organized a number of Age Grades from different Villages' ¹⁸.

Uma Eleazu in Onwuka Njoku talked on Age Grades' ability to sustain societal socio-political stability, when he stated thus, 'In Ohafia the institution is far and away the matrix of socialization, resource mobilization, self-actualization and community development. Uma added to say Age Grade to be a basic institutional form as far as the continuity and stability of the social system are concerned' ¹⁹.

There is popular belief in Ohafia that says, where there is peace is unity. Age Grades have been engaged to enforce peace. This is what Chieka had to say about one of the social responsibilities of the age grade, thus, 'the execution of the law and decisions of the council of elders' ¹⁹, are some of the assigned responsibilities of the age grade. In addition, age grade, 'served as a most useful stabilizing influence in the community' ²⁰.

In Ohafia community, age grade system Ukeji Ogo literally translated to mean, the governing age grade, practically handled matters ranging from inter-village disputes, enforcement and collection of levies, through land cases etc' ²¹. At the Ukeji Ogo age grade the activities of other age grades under them are coordinated.

There is no age grade that does not have rules and regulations guiding them. Such rules and regulations are structured to suit the societal norms thereby instilling stability from the base. In addition, the essence of the rules and regulation is to maintain discipline and orderliness.

The orderly arranged age grades system in Ohafia helped to sustain chains of respect down the line. The cohesion created as a result helped to promote peace. For the good of the community, age grade in the course of fulfilling social responsibility ‘engaged in healthy competition to demonstrate which was the strongest or the most prosperous. In this way, many projects of economic and social importance were quickly accomplished’²². Because the name of an age grade would be at stake no individual or a group of Age grade dare do anything that will tarnish the image of the group. Since an individual could be expelled from an age grade in advent of the violation of the age grade rules care are taken by members not to tarnish image of the age grade.

According to Agha, ‘every age grade has leaders who direct the activities and make age group decisions instrumental’²³. Persons of impeccable character with strong leadership traits are discovered in the age grade, likewise persons with great oratory are nurtured in the age grade. Age grade also provides the needed springboard were men and women are prepared to undertake selfless services.

Age grade had also instilled humility, ‘All the members are equal no matter the individual gifts, wealth, educational background or prowess’²⁴. Humility is a vital attribute for qualitative leadership. Njoku opines, ‘the philosophy of age grade system permeates virtually all fact of Ohafia society and social and interpersonal relations, formal and informal. Most communal levies, entertainments and work are most fruitfully and effectively organized on age grade basis. It is therefore easy to raise money for social development by engaging the age grade has facilitated the process of raising money for the execution of social and economic project. Again, age grade provides a context in which Ohafia people put their differing human resources for maximum use. It is a means of focusing the eyes of the society on its members evaluating their progress and achievement in accordance with established criteria, throughout their lives in this way, every Ohafia man and woman is critically kept conscious of the necessity for personal success and the agony of failure’²⁵. The urge for excellence which has formed the watchword of age grade in Ohafia, has positioned the community to always aspire for success, politically, economically and socially.

CONCLUSION.

The history of age grade formation in Ohafia is one promoted to foster unity in self-help. Evidence has proved, unlike other communities that have suffered series of internal communal crises due to the absence of the age grade intervention.

By offering free farm services, helping to build houses, participating in marriage ceremonies of age mates, raising loan for the needy age mates and even paying the hospital bills of members who are in need, age grades have demonstrated what Dr. Michael Okpara called the spirit of ‘Onye Ahala Nwanneya’, in brotherhood we stand.

The importance of the age grade in conflict resolution cannot be over emphasized. Instead of experiencing crises where none exist in Ohafia land, it has promoted competition as Njoku observed, thus, ‘competition is very keen between age grades. The age grade institution thus evokes group loyalty and solidarity and at the same time inter-personal and inter-age grade rivalry’²⁶. Such rivalry which is healthy for community development has gone beyond sweeping the market square, weeding the path to stream, helping to work in members farm to the construction of feeder roads, building of hospitals, ‘the age grade system provides a context in which Ohafia people put their differing human resources to maximum use’²⁷. The age grade focus on community development has contributed toward placing the community above primordial interest, loyalty to one’s nation is greatly missing in Nigeria context. It is

therefore advisable to not only to emulate the age grade concept but to replicate it for the general well-being of the Nation, more so for the sake of Nation building.

The adoption of the age grade concept could also instill the needed cohesion and stability needed to grow the Nation Nigeria. The introduction of this concept where none exist will stabilize social functions. It will also impact positively on youth's mind-set as the age grade concept will not only offer the youth the much-needed sense of belonging, but arouse in them the patriotic zeal.

Sense of patriotism is what is needed to instill stability, no Nation grows without the patriotic spirit. Recently, government have initiated collaboration with some age grades in Ohafia, with regard to executing rural social projects, while the intervention is commendable it should be encouraged to spread to other places in Nigeria.

Age grade system is an inclusive institution. No one is excluded from participating in community development. This is what Nigeria need. All inclusive system will create sense of belonging. Sense of belonging will trigger patriotic zeal needed to make the Nation great. In Ohafia land over 90% of the social project executed were carried out by the age grades. Age grade in Ohafia have not only brought development to the people, but has created life long avenue toward sustaining development in Ohafia community.

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